

Two different reactions of Rathu Heenati to the brown planthopper in Indonesia

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The reactions of the variety Rathu Heenati to brown planthopper were checked seven times in the greenhouse and once in the paddy field at Sukamandi over a period of 3 years (see table).

Rathu Heenati gave two different reactions; one strain was resistant (scores, 0.2 – 0.9) in the greenhouse and the other was susceptible (8.6 – 8.9). Thus, scientists using Rathu Heenati as a resistant check should ensure that the seed is from the correct accession. ■

Reaction scores of Rathu Heenati to brown planthopper at Sukamandi, Indonesia, 1975–78.

Source	Time of check	Av score ^a	Tested in ^b
1st IRBPHN ^c	May 1975	8.9	GH
Breeding Dep., CRIA, Sukamandi	Jun 1976	0.4	GH
2d IRBPHN ^c	Dec 1976	8.5	GH
IRRI (acc. no. 11730)	Mar 1977	0.4	GH
3d IRBPHN ^c	Oct 1977	0.2	GH
Breeding Dep., CRIA, Sukamandi ^d	Jan 1978	8.5	GH
Breeding Dep., CRIA, Sukamandi ^d	Jan 1978	6.1	F
4th IRBPHN ^c	Dec 1978	0.9	GH

^a1976 Standard Evaluation System for Rice (SES): 1 = little to no damage; 9 = plants dead.

^bGH = greenhouse, F = field.

^cInternational Rice Brown Planthopper Nursery.

^dSeeds obtained from the same source.

Susceptibility of rice cultivars to paddy leaf miner

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The paddy leaf miner *Cerodontha oryzivora* sp. is a minor nursery pest that damages the anterior tips of leaves. But as agroecosystems change, it could become

a major pest.

The maggot remains concealed and feeds on the internal leaf contents, leaving the epidermis intact. The damaged area appears papery with a maggot or pupa inside the infested streak.

An intensive survey was made in the 1978 monsoon season to gain basic information on leaf miner attack on different paddy cultivars. Seventeen

Relative susceptibility of paddy cultivars to paddy leaf miner. Gujarat, India, 1978 kharif.

Cultivar	Plants observed (no.)	Plants infested (%)	Leaves observed (no.)	Leaves infested (%)
<i>Early-maturing</i>				
Shukhvel 20	72	45.8	2697	1.6
118-1-5	77	63.6	2403	3.6
GAUR1	82	59.8	3319	2.2
GTC	75	45.3	1741	2.2
Mochi Rice	96	61.5	748	11.2
GR3	79	38.0	2891	1.4
Ratna	80	53.8	3259	1.6
<i>Medium-maturing</i>				
GAUR10	81	66.7	1954	3.6
GR11	82	58.5	1411	4.1
<i>Late-maturing</i>				
Jaya	75	90.7	1986	7.4
N19	85	77.6	1265	8.2
Salt Culture	94	52.1	2206	2.6
Pankhali 203	80	80.0	1366	6.1
J208	80	68.8	1606	4.1
Kamod 118	76	90.8	1449	8.1
Mahsuri	82	61.0	2521	2.3
GAUR100	86	53.5	1400	4.1

paddy cultivars were grown at the Main Rice Research Station, GAU, Nawagam. From 75 to 100 plants were randomly selected from the plots and the percentage of leaves damaged by leaf miner was determined.

No cultivar was resistant (see table). Plant infestation ranged from 38 to 91%. On the basis of percentage of plants infested, early maturing cultivars were less susceptible than medium- and late-maturing rices. The trend was similar for leaf infestation, which ranged from 1.4 to 3.6% (except in Mochi Rice, which has few leaves). Medium- and late-maturing rices, except Salt Culture, also had higher infestation.

Although late-maturing varieties seemed more susceptible to leaf miner than early ones, results of studies conducted in 1976 by Upadhyay and associates did not reveal a correlation between crop maturity and leaf miner infestation level. ■

Mass rearing of the rice gall midge in the greenhouse in Indonesia

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The rice gall midge *Orseolia oryzae* has been reared in the greenhouse at Bogor, Indonesia, since 1974. The rearing procedure is based on the biology of the

Number of gall midge adults collected per month in the greenhouse. Bogor, Indonesia, 1975–78.

Month	Gall midge adults (thousand)			
	1975	1976	1977	1978
Jan.	1.3	2.8	13.3	30.2
Feb	2.1	2.6	11.1	25.9
Mar	3.9	4.1	10.9	26.4
Apr	7.0	5.1	10.3	21.8
May	4.3	3.4	12.6	26.3
Jun	7.1	4.3	19.8	23.8
Jul	5.7	5.0	26.4	25.6
Aug	7.6	5.4	34.7	28.6
Sep	2.8	10.4	22.8	23.7
Oct	4.5	12.3	24.9	25.0
Nov	3.2	10.7	18.1	20.2
Dec	2.7	12.4	22.0	17.6
Av	4.4	6.5	18.9	24.6
Sex ratio (female: male):	1.7:1	1.4:1	1.4:1	1.4:1

insect and the stage when it feeds on plants.

Results of rearing are presented in the table. The average number of adults collected per month was 4,402 in 1975,

6,540 in 1976, 18,912 in 1977, and 24,594 in 1978. The insects are useful for continuity in mass rearing, varietal screening, and other gall midge experiments. ■

Agriculture). IR30, and OS6 — were compared at 4 rates of N (0, 150, 300, and 450 ppm), replicated 3 times in 10-liter plastic pots that were watered once daily, without flooding. Data on soil water-holding capacity were not collected. Soil analysis before cropping indicated a pH of 6.7, 2.2% organic C, 0.17% total N, 6.7 kg available P/ha, and 238 kg available K/ha.

IR30 had the highest mean harvest Index (86.7%) and differed highly significantly from the other rices ($P < 0.01$) (see table). That implies that IR30 used a greater proportion of the nutrients in the production of grain than of straw. The other cultivars did not differ significantly. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Drought resistance

Screening for harvest index in upland rice in southwestern Nigeria

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Yields of rainfed upland rice are low in the rain forest zone of southwestern Nigeria partly because farmers use OS6, a long-culmed, low-tillering, and lodging-susceptible cultivar that responds poorly to fertilizer nitrogen (N). Lodging adversely affects percentage of filled grains, a major yield component.

The selection criteria suggested for high-yielding, N-responsive semidwarf cultivars include harvest index, ratio of

grain, and biological yield (excluding root weight).

Among the rice accessions screened in the greenhouse, 5 improved cultivars—TOS4164, TOS4172, TOS4632 (from the International Institute of Tropical

Harvest indexes of 5 rice cultivars.^a University of Ife, Ibadan, Nigeria.

Cultivars	Harvest index (%)				Mean
	0 ppm N	150 ppm N	300 ppm N	450 ppm N	
IR30	99.9	115.7	51.3	74.0	86.7 a
TOS4164	75.5	49.3	46.8	64.4	59.0 b
TOS4172	52.0	58.8	62.8	47.0	55.2 b
TOS4632	60.4	55.0	42.5	45.5	50.9 b
OS6	48.7	56.9	63.7	64.4	58.4 b

^a Standard error = 13.0. Coefficient of variation = 21.0%. Means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Adverse soils tolerance

IR42: a modern variety suited to the small rice farmer

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Small farmers lack the resources to provide the water control and management inputs needed to extract the high yield potential of modern varieties. To benefit from the green revolution, they need varieties with built-in tolerance for adverse environmental factors, i.e., too little or too much water, diseases and insects, and nutrient deficiencies and soil toxicities. The Philippine-named IR42 is the closest we have to such a variety.

IR42 has good agronomic characteristics. It yields well at low levels of nitrogen and phosphorus

fertilizers and has moderate tolerance for salinity, alkalinity, iron toxicity, excess organic matter, and zinc deficiency. It is resistant to rice tungro

virus, grassy stunt, bacterial blight and blast, and has intermediate resistance to sheath blight and *Cercospora* leaf spot. It has resistance to biotypes 1 and 2 of

Performance of IR42 and of other IR varieties on 6 problem soils. Philippines, 1978 dry and wet seasons.

Problem	Variety	Rating ^a	Grain yield (t/ha)	Location
Salinity	IR42	MT	5.6	Sinacaban, Misamis Occidental
	IR4630-22	T	5.1	
Iron toxicity	IR42	MT	4.6	Malinao, Camarines Sur
	IR36	T	2.2	
Peat soil	IR42	MT	4.2	Colorado, Agusan del Norte
	IR34	T	2.4	
Nitrogen deficiency	IR42	—	4.6	IRRI
	IR34	—	1.2	
Phosphorus deficiency	IR42	MT	3.9	Pangil, Laguna
	IR20	T	4.2	
Zinc deficiency ^b	IR42	MT	5.4	Gen. Santos, South Cotabato
	IR34	T	5.0	

^aMT = moderately tolerant, T = tolerant. ^bPartly corrected by zinc oxide dip.